

Preserved Alpha Activity in Resting-State EEG Underlies Cognitive Reserve and Semantic Fluency in Multiple Sclerosis

Alexandra Anagnostopoulou ^{a,b,1}, Panagiotis E. Kartsidis ^{a,2}, Nefeli Tsoukaki ^{a,3}, Maria Karagianni ^{a,4}, Nikos Melanitis ^{c,5}, Athanasia Liozidou ^{d,6}, Ioannis Nikolaidis ^{f,7}, Christos Chatzichristos ^{c,g,8}, Vahe Poghosyan ^{h,9}, Nikolaos Grigoriadis ^{i,10}, Panagiotis D. Bamidis ^{a,11}, Charis Styliadis ^{a,12,*}

^a Medical Physics and Digital Innovation Laboratory, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

^b Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

^c Innovation & Incubation Center KU Leuven, AINIGMA Technologies, Leuven, Belgium

^d Laboratory of Cognitive Neuroscience and Clinical Neuropsychology, Scientific College of Greece, Athens, Greece

^e 1st Neurology Department, Athens Medical School, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens

^f Department of Neurology, Hippokration General Hospital of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

^g Department of Electrical Engineering, STADIUS Center for Dynamical Systems, Signal Processing and Data Analytics, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

^h Department of Neurophysiology, National Neuroscience Institute, King Fahad Medical City, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

ⁱ Multiple Sclerosis Center, 2nd Department of Neurology, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

* Corresponding author at: Medical Physics and Digital Innovation Laboratory, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, University Campus, PO Box 376, 54124, Thessaloniki, Greece

E-mail address: cstyliadis@auth.gr (C. Styliadis)

¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9578-7552>

² <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7835-4763>

³ <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-3700-1477>

⁴ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4492-4382>

⁵ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3820-037X>

⁶ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8895-819X>

⁷ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4054-7559>

⁸ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9054-5340>

⁹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2338-1681>

¹⁰ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4278-3301>

¹¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9936-5805>

¹² <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7383-2439>

Abstract

Background:

Cognitive reserve (CR) is known to mitigate cognitive decline in people with multiple sclerosis (PwMS), yet the neurophysiological mechanisms supporting this effect remain poorly understood. Alpha (α) oscillatory activity has been proposed as an index of neural efficiency and resilience. This study examined whether preserved resting-state α oscillatory activity underlies CR's influence on cognition, focusing on the reserve-sensitive domain of semantic verbal fluency (SVF).

Methods:

Sixty-four PwMS and forty-six matched healthy controls (HC) underwent resting-state electroencephalography to estimate global spectral power. CR was assessed using the CR Index questionnaire, while verbal fluency was measured using standard procedures. Regression, mediation, and moderated mediation analyses examined associations among CR, spectral power, and verbal fluency, adjusted for demographic, clinical, and patient-reported factors. Physical disability and perceived disease were tested as moderators.

Results:

PwMS showed reduced upper α power (10.5-13 Hz) compared with HC, which was associated with lower CR levels and poorer SVF performance. Mediation analyses showed that upper α power fully mediated the effect of CR on SVF, including leisure activity-derived CR. Although the moderated mediation models were non-significant, conditional effects indicated the mediation was significant at moderate levels of physical disability and perceived disease impact.

Conclusions:

These findings demonstrate that preserved upper α oscillatory activity constitutes a neurophysiological pathway through which CR supports semantic access and retrieval in PwMS. Upper α power emerges as a promising electrophysiological marker of resilience in MS and a potential target of reserve-building interventions. The study is registered with ClinicalTrials.gov under Identifier NCT04806568.

Keywords: Cognitive Reserve, Multiple Sclerosis, EEG, Alpha Oscillations, Global Spectral Power, Semantic Fluency, Mediation/Moderation

1. Introduction

Cognitive decline affects approximately two-thirds of people with multiple sclerosis (PwMS), profoundly impacting various aspects of daily living, employment, and quality of life (Benedict et al., 2020). It is typically domain-specific, most commonly affecting memory and information processing speed (Benedict et al., 2020). Word-finding difficulties, reflecting inefficiencies in lexico-semantic retrieval, are amongst the earliest and most frequent complaints (Saldert et al., 2025). However, cognitive profiles vary considerably across individuals, even under comparable levels of brain pathology (Eijlers et al., 2018), suggesting that factors beyond structural damage, such as cognitive reserve (CR), modulate cognitive decline (Sumowski & Leavitt, 2013). Understanding such resilience mechanisms, particularly those preserving lexico-semantic retrieval, is essential for improving functional outcomes in PwMS (Leavitt et al., 2025).

CR refers to the capacity to maintain cognitive performance despite pathology, fostered through cognitively enriching experiences (education, complex occupations, and intellectually stimulating activities) (Stern et al., 2020). In MS, a higher CR is linked to a reduced risk of cognitive impairment (Amato et al., 2019; Santangelo, Altieri, Enzinger, et al., 2019), and greater resilience to lesion and grey matter damage (Santangelo, Altieri, Gallo, et al., 2019), with particularly strong effects on semantic verbal fluency (SVF), a core measure of lexico-semantic access and retrieval. However, despite substantial evidence for CR's behavioral (Amato et al., 2019; Santangelo, Altieri, Enzinger, et al., 2019) and clinical (Santangelo, Altieri, Gallo, et al., 2019) benefits, the neurophysiological mechanisms supporting functions such as SVF remain insufficiently understood.

At the neuronal level, CR is thought to rely on two neuroplastic mechanisms: functional preservation (Fuchs et al., 2019; Stern et al., 2020; Sumowski et al., 2009), where greater neuronal efficiency protects against pathology, and adaptive compensation (Bizzo et al., 2021; Stern et al., 2020), where alternative networks are recruited to counteract neurodegeneration. Evidence favors preservation, as functional imaging studies show that preserved regional functional organization mitigates the impact of structural damage on processing speed (Fuchs et al., 2019) and that task-positive networks engaged during N-Back tasks mediate the CR-processing speed relationship (Sumowski et al., 2009). However, how CR supports lexico-semantic functions, such as verbal fluency, remains unclear, as its neural dynamics are best captured through electrophysiological measures that directly reflect oscillatory efficiency and network organization.

Resting-state magneto/electroencephalography (rsM/EEG) allows direct and temporally precise quantification of neural activity, providing complementary insights into the mechanisms of preservation and compensation. The well-established connection between neuronal slowing, particularly in the alpha

(α) band, and poorer cognitive performance across domains (De Cock et al., 2023; Schoonhoven et al., 2019) suggests that preserved α oscillatory activity reflects cortical efficiency. Furthermore, electrophysiological studies in individuals with subjective or objective memory complaints show that increases in upper α power are associated with preservation (Babiloni et al., 2020; Lopez et al., 2024), whereas decreases indicate compensation (Babiloni et al., 2020, 2021), supporting the notion that α power represents a neural marker of CR. Collectively, these findings position α oscillatory activity as a plausible neurophysiological substrate of CR, although whether preservation of α activity modulates the CR-SVF relationship in PwMS remains unexamined.

To address this gap, we investigated the electrophysiological mechanisms underlying reserve-related cognitive performance in PwMS. We hypothesized that the preservation of α oscillatory activity represents a functional mechanism through which CR influences SVF. We tested whether global α oscillatory activity mediates the CR-SVF relationship and, to frame this clinically, explored whether this mediation is moderated by physical disability and perceived disease impact. Establishing CR's electrophysiological markers in MS could clarify how reserve influences cognition and provide new tools for assessing cognitive resilience.

2. Methods

2.1 Participants

Data were obtained from 64 PwMS and 46 age- and sex-matched healthy controls (HC) who were enrolled in the MS-NEUROPLAST clinical trial (ClinicalTrials.gov identifier: NCT04806568) (Styliadis et al., 2024). PwMS were recruited through the Multiple Sclerosis Centre of the 2nd Department of Neurology at AHEPA University Hospital of Thessaloniki, the Department of Neurology at Hippokraton General Hospital of Thessaloniki, Greece, and via affiliated private neurologists. The study was approved by the Research Ethics and Deontology Committee of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Protocol No. 254350/2020; approval 1 December 2020) and conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. All participants gave written informed consent before participation. Detailed inclusion and exclusion criteria are provided in the Supplementary Information. Physical disability was evaluated using the Expanded Disability Status Scale (EDSS) (Kurtzke, 1983) .

2.2 Cognitive reserve and neuropsychological battery

CR was assessed using the CR index questionnaire (CRIq), adapted and standardised for the Greek population (Maiovis et al., 2016). CRIq quantifies CR levels in three proxy domains: i) educational attainment (years of study; CRI-Edu), ii) occupational complexity (type and years of paid work; CRI-Work), and iii) engagement in intellectually enriching leisure activities (frequency and years of leisure

activities such as reading books, watching films, doing household chores, driving, socialising, using technology, etc.; CRI-Leis).

Cognitive performance was evaluated using an extensive test battery (see Supplementary Information). The present study focuses on verbal fluency (VF) and particularly on SVF, but also considers phonemic fluency as both share partly overlapping cognitive processes (Biesbroek et al., 2016). VF was assessed with the Verbal Fluency tests (Lezak et al., 2004), measuring phonemic (Chi-Sigma-Alpha, XSA) and semantic (Animals-Fruit-Objects, AFO) tasks. Scores were z-transformed using Greek normative data to adjust for age and education effects (Kosmidis et al., 2004).

Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) included fatigue (Modified Fatigue Impact Scale, MFIS) (Fisk et al., 1994), depression (Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale-21 Items depression subscale, DASS-21ds) (Antony et al., 1998), and disease impact (Multiple Sclerosis Impact Scale-29 Items, MSIS-29) (Hobart et al., 2001) in PwMS.

2.3 EEG acquisition

rsEEG activity was recorded for 7 minutes using a high-density Nihon Kohden EEG acquisition system at a sampling rate of 1000 Hz. Recordings were obtained using two passive 128-channel R-NET caps (Brain Products, size 55 and 57 cm), with electrode impedance maintained below 20 k Ω . All sessions took place in a sound-attenuated, electrically shielded booth at the Medical Physics and Digital Innovation Laboratory, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece. Participants sat comfortably, eyes closed, in the dark and were instructed to remain relaxed and minimise movement throughout the recording.

2.4 EEG preprocessing

EEG preprocessing was conducted using the MNE-Python library (Gramfort et al., 2013). The continuous EEG signal was band-pass filtered using a 1 Hz high-pass FIR filter and a 100 Hz low-pass FIR filter. Line noise was removed using a set of five IIR notch filters centred at 50 Hz and its harmonics. The filtered signals were visually inspected to identify channels with poor signal quality.

Independent component analysis (ICA; Infomax algorithm) (Lee et al., 1999) was applied to attenuate ocular, muscular, and other physiological or mechanical artifacts. Prior to ICA, the data were pre-whitened via principal component analysis (PCA). PCA was computed to retain at least two components, whereas the number of ICA components was defined as those explaining around 99% of the total signal variance (median = 48 components, IQE = 18.5). ICA components were automatically classified using the ICLabel algorithm (Li et al., 2022), and components identified as artifactual with a probability over 70% were removed before reconstructing the cleaned EEG signal (Asogbon et al., 2023).

The reconstructed signal was subsequently segmented into 4-second epochs. Using the Autoreject MNE plugin (Jas et al., 2017) lower-quality epochs were automatically rejected or interpolated based on a subject-specific calibration of the first 20 epochs (Delorme, 2023). Remaining epochs were evaluated through visual inspection of their power spectral density (PSD), and epochs exhibiting marked deviations from an individual's average PSD were removed. On average, 5.7 minutes of data were retained per participant (median = 87 epochs; IQR = 20.75).

The resulting epochs were imported into the sLORETA/eLORETA software (Pascual-Marqui et al., 1994). The data were transformed into the frequency domain and projected to cortical sources using standardised low-resolution electromagnetic tomography (sLORETA) (Pascual-Marqui et al., 1994). Source-space current density estimates were obtained for the delta (δ ; 1–4 Hz), theta (θ ; 4–7 Hz), lower-alpha (α_1 ; 7.5–10 Hz), and upper-alpha (α_2 ; 10.5–13 Hz) bands. Although the primary hypothesis concerned α -band activity, the δ and θ bands were included due to their established relevance to neuropathology in PwMS (Babiloni et al., 2016; Keune et al., 2017; Schoonhoven et al., 2019). Global spectral power for each band was subsequently estimated as the grand-average source activation mean across participants.

2.5 Statistics

Neuropsychological performance and global spectral power were compared between PwMS and HC using JASP (version 0.18.3; JASP Team 2025) with independent-sample *t*-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests, depending on normality assessed by the Shapiro–Wilk test. For spectral power analyses, *p*-values were corrected for multiple comparisons using the false discovery rate (FDR) method (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995).

Voxel-wise permutation analysis identified cortical regions contributing to group differences in global spectral power. Specifically, the statistical nonparametric mapping method (SnPM) (Nichols & Holmes, 2002) was applied to create the empirical *t*-test distribution of between-group differences, estimated at each permutation, to reject the null hypothesis of equality between groups for the frequency band exhibiting significant differences at the global level. Permutation analysis was conducted using sLORETA/eLORETA (Pascual-Marqui et al., 1994).

For PwMS, linear and logistic regression models examined associations between CRIq and demographics, disease-related characteristics, PROMs, global spectral power in frequency bands that differed significantly from HC, and cognitive performance. Models for spectral power and cognitive performance were adjusted for age, sex, MS type, disease duration, fatigue, and depression, which are known to confound cognitive performance (Langdon et al., 2012). Observed *p*-values were adjusted for

multiple comparisons via FDR. When associations reached significance, a follow-up multiple regression including all three CRIq subscales was conducted to determine the CR subdomain exerting the strongest influence. Regression analyses were conducted in JASP (version 0.18.3).

To investigate whether spectral power constitutes a mechanism through which CR influences VF cognition in PwMS, a mediation analysis was performed using the PROCESS macro model 4 (Hayes, 2013) in SPSS (version 29.0; IBM Corp). In the present study, CRIq served as the independent variable, the global spectral power of bands significantly associated with CRIq as mediators, and cognitive performance scores significantly correlated with CRIq as dependent variables (Figure 1A). Age, sex, MS type, disease duration, fatigue (MFIS), and depression (DASS-21ds) were included as covariates due to their established influence on cognition (Langdon et al., 2012). Indirect effects were estimated using percentile bootstrapping (10000 iterations) to derive 95% confidence intervals (CI), with effects considered significant when the CI did not include 0. To address heteroscedasticity, the Cribari-Neto heteroscedasticity-consistent standard error estimator (Cribari-Neto & da Silva, 2011) was applied. When the overall mediation model was significant, subsequent analyses (post hoc mediation models) were performed for each CRI subscale to determine the primary contributors to the effect.

To frame the mediation effects in the context of physical disability and disease impact (Stein et al., 2023; Stern et al., 2020), a moderated mediation analysis was conducted using the PROCESS macro model 59 (Hayes, 2013) in SPSS (version 29.0; IBM Corp) (Figure 1B). EDSS or MSIS-29 (physical and psychological) served as moderators of all mediation paths. The analyses estimated conditional direct and indirect effects across disability or disease impact levels (low, moderate, high), centred on the 16th, 50th, and 84th percentiles. As in the primary mediation models, age, sex, MS type, disease duration, fatigue, and depression were again entered as covariates, and percentile bootstrapping with 95% CI and the Cribari-Neto estimator were applied.

Unless otherwise specified, statistical significance was defined as $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed) for all analyses.

Figure 1. (A) Graphical representation of the mediation model illustrating the effects of CRIq (independent variable) on verbal fluency (dependent variable) through global spectral power (mediator), adjusted for age, sex, disease duration, fatigue, and depression. The total effect represents the overall CRIq–verbal fluency relationship; the direct effect (c') reflects the portion independent of spectral power;

the indirect effect (*ab*) quantifies how CRIq influences verbal fluency via the CRIq → spectral power → verbal fluency pathway. The *a*-path quantifies the CRIq-spectral power association, while the *b*-path captures the effect of spectral power on verbal fluency. (B) Graphical representation of the moderated mediation analysis extending (A), testing whether physical disability (EDSS) or perceived disease impact (MSIS-29 physical and psychological) modifies any of the model paths. Interaction terms are indicated for each path (*a*, *b*, and direct). Conditional effects were estimated at low, moderate, and high levels of the moderator (16th, 50th, and 84th percentiles). Abbreviations: CRIq: Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire; MFIS: Modified Fatigue Impact Scale; DASS-21ds: Depression, Anxiety, Stress Scale – 21 Items depression subscale; EDSS: Expanded Disability Status Scale; MSIS-29: Multiple Sclerosis Impact Scale – 29 Items.

3. Results

3.1 Population characteristics

Participant characteristics are summarised in Table 1. The groups were matched for age and sex, though PwMS had fewer years of education (3.6 on average). PwMS showed lower total CRIq ($p < 0.001$), and lower scores on the education ($p = 0.005$), work activity ($p = 0.008$), and leisure activities ($p = 0.001$) subscales. They performed worse on both verbal fluency tasks ($p < 0.001$) and reported higher levels of fatigue ($p = 0.005$) and depression ($p < 0.001$) compared with HC.

Table 1. Demographics, disease-related information, cognitive performance and responses to PROMs from PwMS and HC.

	PwMS (N=64)	HC (N=46)	<i>p</i>
Demographics			
Age (years)	41.64 (12.20)	39.09 (10.91)	0.261
Sex (women)	52 (81.25%)	33 (71.74%)	0.240
Education (years)*	16 (4)	18 (3)	<0.001
Disease-related characteristics			
MS subtype (RRMS/PMS)	47/17 (73.4/26.6%)	—	—
EDSS	3.02 (1.65)	—	—
Disease Duration (years)*	7.5 (10.25)	—	—
Cognitive performance per assessment (z-scored)			
CRIq*	-0.34 (1.04)	0.36 (0.73)	<0.001
CRI-Edu	0.18 (0.76)	0.62 (0.86)	0.005
CRI-Work*	-0.38 (0.95)	0.10 (0.62)	0.008
CRI-Leis	-0.56 (0.97)	0.02 (0.77)	0.001
XSA	-0.55 (1.15)	0.19 (0.79)	<0.001
AFO	-0.07 (0.98)	0.78 (0.89)	<0.001
PROMs			
MFIS	34.67 (19.13)	25.32 (12.80)	0.005
DASS-21ds*	4 (7.50)	1.5 (3.75)	0.006
MSIS-29	54.92 (18.59)	—	—

Sex and MS subtypes are indicated as N (%). The mean and standard deviation are presented for most of the remaining variables, whereas * denotes the cases where the median and the interquartile range are presented. Significant differences between the groups ($p < 0.05$) are denoted with bold type.

Abbreviations: RRMS: Relapsing-Remitting MS; PMS: Progressive MS; EDSS: Expanded Disability Status Scale; CRIq: Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire; CRI-Edu: Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire – Education subscale; CRI-Work: Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire – Work Activity subscale; CRI-Leis: Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire – Leisure activities subscale; XSA: Chi-Sigma-Alpha Phonemic Verbal Fluency Test; AFO: Animals-Fruit-Objects Semantic Verbal Fluency Test; PROMs: Patient/Participant-Reported Outcome Measures; MFIS: Modified Fatigue Impact Scale; DASS-21ds: Depression, Anxiety, Stress Scale – 21 Items depression subscale; MSIS-29: Multiple Sclerosis Impact Scale – 29 Items.

3.2 Global spectral power

Group comparisons of global spectral power revealed significantly reduced $\alpha 2$ power in PwMS versus HC ($t = -2.92$, adjusted $p = 0.017$). Figure 2 displays the grand-averaged global relative power across the four frequency bands per group.

Figure 2. Grand-averaged global spectral power in the δ , θ , $\alpha 1$, and $\alpha 2$ frequency bands for PwMS and HC. The error bars indicate the standard deviation for each group, while * signifies a significant difference between groups with $p < 0.05$. P-values were adjusted for multiple comparisons via the FDR method.

3.3 Regional spectral power

The permutation analysis of α_2 regional spectral power identified significant group differences (HC vs. PwMS) in 1173 voxels ($p < 0.05$; Figure 3). These differences were more pronounced in the left hemisphere and involved prefrontal (superior, medial, and middle frontal gyrus, straight gyrus), central (precentral and postcentral gyrus), parietal (superior and inferior parietal lobules, angular gyrus, precuneus), temporal (inferior, middle, and superior temporal gyrus), temporo-occipital (fusiform gyrus), and occipital regions (cuneus, superior, middle, and inferior occipital gyrus). In the right hemisphere, differences were less extensive but followed a similar pattern, involving prefrontal (superior, medial, and middle frontal gyrus), central (precentral gyrus and paracentral lobule), parietal (superior parietal lobule), temporal (inferior and middle temporal gyrus), temporo-occipital (fusiform gyrus), and occipital regions (inferior and middle occipital lobe, and lingual gyrus). Full details on Brodmann areas, cluster sizes, T-values, and peak coordinates are provided in Supplementary Table S1.

Figure 3. Axial, sagittal, and coronal views of the differences between HC and PwMS in terms of grand-averaged regional spectral power in the α_2 band at $p < 0.01$ adjusted for multiple comparisons using the FDR method. The L and R represent the left and right hemispheres, respectively. The colour scale

represents *t*-values, with positive *t*-values indicating decreased activations in PwMS. The coronal view shows the anterior (top) and posterior (bottom) of the brain.

3.4 CRIq correlates

Associations between CRIq and demographics, disease variables, PROMs, global power, and cognition are summarised in Table 2 and supplementary Table S2. CRIq was positively correlated with sex, mainly reflecting higher leisure activities-derived CR in women. As expected, CRIq correlated strongly with education. Lower CR was observed in progressive MS forms and among participants with higher depression, although these associations did not remain significant after correction for multiple comparisons. CR was positively correlated with $\alpha 2$ global spectral power and SVF (AFO). The association with $\alpha 2$ power was driven by leisure activities-derived CR, while the SVF association reflected overall CR, with positive trends for both education and leisure activities.

Table 2. Association between CRIq and demographics, disease-related information, PROMs, global relative power, and verbal fluency performance at $p < 0.05$, adjusted for multiple comparisons via the FDR method.

	CRIq			CRI-Edu		CRI-Work		CRI-Leis	
	β	<i>p</i>	<i>adj. p</i>	β	<i>p</i>	β	<i>p</i>	β	<i>p</i>
Demographics									
Age	-0.171	0.177	0.322	—	—	—	—	—	—
Sex ¹	1.360	0.004	0.015	-0.171	0.605	0.683	0.123	0.986	0.034
Education	0.561	<0.001	<0.001	0.676	<0.001	0.040	0.521	0.135	0.151
Disease-Related Information									
MS type ¹	-0.713	0.029	0.058	—	—	—	—	—	—
EDSS	-0.156	0.219	0.29	—	—	—	—	—	—
Disease Duration	-0.148	0.244	0.29	—	—	—	—	—	—
PROMs									
MFIS	-0.221	0.079	0.119	—	—	—	—	—	—
DASS-21ds	-0.277	0.027	0.058	—	—	—	—	—	—
MSIS-29	-0.245	0.051	0.087	—	—	—	—	—	—
Global spectral power²									
$\alpha 2$	0.420	0.003	0.015	0.080	0.523	0.179	0.164	0.294	0.035
Cognitive performance²									
XSA	-0.019	0.951	0.951	—	—	—	—	—	—
AFO	0.323	0.008	0.024	0.197	0.073	0.030	0.788	0.212	0.078

When a significant association between a variable and CRIq occurred, the relation between the same variable and the CRIq subscales was also investigated. Bold type denotes significance. ¹ indicates that the logistic regression was applied. ² indicates that regressions with variables of this category were adjusted for age and sex, MS type, disease duration, MFIS, and DASS-21ds. Abbreviations: CRIq: Cognitive

Reserve Index questionnaire; CRI-Edu: Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire – Education subscale; CRI-Work: Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire – Work activity subscale; CRI-Leis: Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire – Leisure activities subscale; adj: adjusted; EDSS: Expanded Disability Status Scale; PROMs: Patient/Participant-Reported Outcome Measures; MFIS: Modified Fatigue Impact Scale; DASS-21ds: Depression, Anxiety, Stress Scale – 21 Items depression subscale; MSIS-29: Multiple Sclerosis Impact Scale – 29 Items; XSA: Chi-Sigma-Alpha Phonemic Fluency Test; AFO: Animals-Fruit-Objects Semantic Fluency Test.

3.5 Mediation and moderated mediation analyses

The mediation analysis results examining the relationships among CRIq, $\alpha 2$ global spectral power, and SVF are summarised in Figure 4, Table 3, and Supplementary Tables S3–S5.

A significant total effect of CRIq on SVF (AFO) was found ($c, p = 0.013$). The direct path was non-significant ($c', p = 0.057$), suggesting this relationship is not entirely independent from $\alpha 2$ oscillatory activity, whereas the indirect effect (CRIq \rightarrow $\alpha 2$ \rightarrow SVF; $ab, p < 0.05$) was significant, indicating that $\alpha 2$ global spectral power accounted for 30.2% (estimated as the ratio of indirect effect to total effect or ab/c) of the CR-SVF relationship. The two individual paths (Figure 4) showed that higher CR was associated with higher $\alpha 2$ spectral power ($p = 0.001$), which, in turn, was related to better SVF performance ($p = 0.013$).

Among the CRIq subscales, only CRI-Edu and CRI-Leis, which showed positive trends with SVF, were further analysed. For CRI-Edu, the non-significant association with $\alpha 2$ spectral power restricted mediation testing to the direct path, which was also non-significant ($p = 0.109$). This suggests that the CRI-Edu-SVF link is neither modulated by nor independent of $\alpha 2$ power. In contrast, for CRI-Leis, the significant correlation with $\alpha 2$ spectral power directed the focus to the indirect path, indicating that CRI-Leis influences SVF indirectly, through $\alpha 2$ oscillatory activity, which accounted for 37.1% (ab/c) of their association.

Table 3. Summary of the mediation analysis for PwMS regarding the effects of different paths.

Effect	Path	Coeff.	SE	t	95% CI		p	
					Lower	Upper		
Total	CRIq \rightarrow SVF	c	0.437	0.170	2.572	0.097	0.777	0.013
Indirect	CRIq \rightarrow $\alpha 2$ \rightarrow SFV	ab	0.132	0.075	—	0.016	0.306	< 0.05
Direct	CRIq \rightarrow SVF	c'	0.305	0.157	1.947	-0.009	0.618	0.057
Total	CRI-Edu \rightarrow SVF	c	0.276	0.155	1.778	-0.035	0.587	0.081
Indirect	CRI-Edu \rightarrow $\alpha 2$ \rightarrow SVF	ab	0.041	0.060	—	-0.064	0.175	> 0.05
Direct	CRI-Edu \rightarrow SVF	c'	0.235	0.144	1.628	-0.565	1.887	0.109
Total	CRI-Leis \rightarrow SVF	c	0.232	0.165	1.409	-0.098	0.563	0.164
Indirect	CRI-Leis \rightarrow $\alpha 2$ \rightarrow SVF	ab	0.086	0.049	—	0.011	0.198	< 0.05

Direct	CRI-Leis → SVF	c'	0.146	0.167	0.875	-0.189	0.482	0.385
--------	----------------	------	-------	-------	-------	--------	-------	-------

The bold type denotes significance, determined by 0 being out of CI bounds (as defined by the bootstrap-derived CI lower and upper levels). Abbreviations: Coeff.: Coefficient; SE: Standard Error; CI: Confidence Interval; CRIq: Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire; CRI-Edu: Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire – Education subscale; CRIq-Leis: Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire – Leisure activities subscale; SVF: Semantic Verbal Fluency test.

Figure 4. Statistical diagram of the effects of the mediation analysis with CRIq as the independent variable, α_2 global spectral power as the mediator, performance on SVF as the dependent variable, and age, sex, MS type, disease duration, MFIS, and DASS-21ds as covariates. The mediation analysis explores three different paths: total (c , which indicates the relationship between CRIq and SVF while ignoring the effect of α_2 global spectral power), direct (c' , which indicates if the relationship between CRIq and SVF is independent of the effect of α_2 global spectral power), and indirect (ab , which indicates whether CRIq's influence on α_2 global spectral power can be transmitted to SVF through the CRIq → α_2 → SVF path). Alternatively, the indirect effect can be estimated as the product of paths a and b (hence denoted as ab). In our model, the total ($c = 0.437, 95\% \text{ CI} = [0.097, 0.777], p = 0.013$) and indirect ($ab = 0.132, 95\% \text{ CI} = [0.016, 0.304], p < 0.05$) effects are significant, indicating that the relationship between CRIq and SVF is dependent on α_2 global spectral power, with α_2 explaining 30.2% of the relationship, as CR appears to exert influence on SVF entirely through α_2 , i.e., individuals with higher CR have higher α_2

spectral power and thus higher performance on SVF. Abbreviations: CI: Confidence Interval; CRIq: Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire; SVF: Semantic Verbal Fluency; MFIS: Modified Fatigue Impact Scale; DASS-21ds: Depression, Anxiety, Stress Scale – 21 Items – depression subscale.

Moderated mediation models tested whether CR's direct and indirect effects on SVF varied with physical disability (EDSS) or disease impact (MSIS-29 Physical and Psychological). None of the interaction terms in the mediator or outcome models were significant (see Supplementary Tables S6-S8), indicating no formal evidence of moderation of the individual paths. However, inspection of the conditional effects suggested potential patterns warranting further exploration (Hayes & Little, 2022) (Table 4).

For EDSS and MSIS-29 Physical, the direct CR-SVF relationship remained non-significant across all levels of disability and disease impact. In contrast, the conditional indirect effects indicated that the CRIq → $\alpha 2$ → SVF pathway was significant only at moderate levels of physical disability and disease impact (EDSS centered at 3 and MSIS-29 Physical centered at 35), but not at low or high levels.

When the MSIS-29 Psychological subscale served as a moderator, a similar pattern emerged for the indirect effect, i.e., significant at moderate psychological impact (MSIS-29 Psychological centered at 17). However, a distinct pattern was observed for the direct effect, which became significant only under high psychological impact (MSIS-29 Psychological centered at 23.6: $p = 0.039$). This implies that under higher psychological burden, the CR-SVF association may rely on mechanisms other than $\alpha 2$ oscillatory activity.

Table 4. Conditional direct (CRIq to SVF accounting for the influence of $\alpha 2$ power) and indirect mediation (CRIq to SVF through $\alpha 2$ power) paths across low, medium, and high levels of EDSS and MSIS-29 Physical and Psychological, with age, sex, MS type, disease duration, MFIS, and DASS-21ds as covariates.

Moderator	Coeff.	SE	<i>t</i>	95% CI		<i>p</i>	
				Lower	Upper		
Conditional direct effects of CRIq on SVF							
EDSS	1.2	0.351	0.251	1.396	-0.153	0.854	0.169
	3	0.313	0.165	1.891	-0.019	0.644	0.064
	5	0.271	0.193	1.404	-0.166	0.657	0.166
Conditional indirect effects of CRIq on SVF through $\alpha 2$ spectral power							
EDSS	1.2	0.100	0.101	—	-0.042	0.341	> 0.05
	3	0.133	0.082	—	0.010	0.325	< 0.05
	5	0.174	0.168	—	-0.024	0.607	> 0.05
Conditional direct effects of CRIq on SVF							
MSIS-29 Physical	22.4	0.302	0.233	1.294	-0.166	0.769	0.201
	35	0.303	0.172	1.760	-0.084	0.648	0.084
	53.2	0.304	0.188	1.620	-0.073	0.681	0.111
Conditional indirect effects of CRIq on SVF through $\alpha 2$ spectral power							
MSIS-29 Physical	22.4	0.083	0.096	—	-0.029	0.331	> 0.05
	35	0.120	0.081	—	0.005	0.316	< 0.05
	53.2	0.188	0.134	—	-0.013	0.503	> 0.05

		Conditional direct effects of CRIq on SVF					
MSIS-29	11.4	0.219	0.219	1.002	-0.22	0.659	0.321
	17	0.312	0.159	1.958	-0.008	0.632	0.056
	23.6	0.421	0.199	2.117	0.022	0.820	0.039
Psychological		Conditional indirect effects of CRIq on SVF through $\alpha 2$ spectral power					
	11.4	0.094	0.099	—	-0.028	0.345	> 0.05
	17	0.117	0.078	—	0.004	0.299	< 0.05
	23.6	0.147	0.121	—	-0.014	0.453	> 0.05

The bold type denotes significance, determined by 0 being out of CI bounds (as defined by the bootstrap-derived CI lower and upper levels). The low levels of the moderators are centred around the 16th percentile, the moderate levels around the 50th percentile, and the high levels around the 84th percentile. Abbreviations: Coeff: Coefficient; SE: Standard Error; EDSS: Expanded Disability Status Scale; MSIS-29: Multiple Sclerosis Impact Scale-29 items; CRIq: Cognitive Reserve Index questionnaire; SVF: Semantic Verbal Fluency; MFIS: Modified Fatigue Impact Scale; DASS-21ds: Depression, Anxiety, Stress Scale-21 items depression subscale; SE: Standard Error; CI: Confidence Interval.

4. Discussion

In PwMS, $\alpha 2$ spectral power fully mediated the relationship between CR and semantic verbal fluency (SVF), indicating that preserved $\alpha 2$ global activity represents a neural mechanism through which CR supports semantic processing. This mediation remained significant at moderate physical disability (EDSS) and perceived disease impact (MSIS-29), suggesting that the effect reflects $\alpha 2$'s modulating role rather than the absence of symptoms. In addition, neuronal slowing, reflected by reduced $\alpha 2$ power relative to HC, was associated with lower CR levels, positioning $\alpha 2$ oscillatory activity as a potential electrophysiological marker of reserve.

Our findings offer novel evidence that $\alpha 2$ power underlies the expression of CR in MS, accounting for 30.2% of the CR-SVF relationship and 37.1% of the association between leisure activity-derived CR and SVF. Previous MS studies have shown that CR primarily moderates the impact of structural damage on SVF (Santangelo, Altieri, Gallo, et al., 2019). Our findings extend this by delineating the neurophysiological substrate supporting this effect. Preserved $\alpha 2$ power reflects the cortical efficiency through which CR maintains SVF, consistent with fMRI evidence linking CR-related preservation to processing speed (Fuchs et al., 2019; Sumowski et al., 2009). Individuals with higher CR, through greater neuronal efficiency, appear less susceptible to neuronal slowing, thereby maintaining lexico-semantic access. Thus, CR exerts a stronger protective influence on semantic than phonemic fluency, consistent with its greater influence on memory (Rocca et al., 2019; Sumowski & Leavitt, 2013). Preserving SVF is important beyond word-finding ability (Leavitt et al., 2025), as semantic knowledge supports the acquisition of new episodic verbal memories (Greenberg & Verfaellie, 2010; Leavitt et al., 2025).

Together, these findings highlight the potential of reserve-building interventions to maintain not only verbal fluency but also broader cognitive processes dependent on semantic integrity.

Although the formal test did not reveal significant moderation of the mediation, the pattern of conditional indirect effects suggests that the influence of $\alpha 2$ power on the CR-SVF relationship varies across levels of physical disability. The mediation was absent at minimal disability (EDSS < 2), emerged at moderate levels, and became non-significant again at higher levels (EDSS > 4), consistent with evidence that CR's protective effects diminish as disease advances (Rocca et al., 2019). These findings indicate that physical disability levels should be considered when referring PwMS to leisure-focused rehabilitation programs. Individuals with greater disability likely exhibit reduced neuroplastic capacity, limiting the benefits of such interventions (Chiaravalloti et al., 2015; Schoonheim et al., 2015). Conversely, the absence of mediation under minimal disability supports the notion that CR's protective effect is less pronounced when disease burden is low (Sumowski & Leavitt, 2013). Such individuals may benefit most from early reserve-building interventions designed to strengthen the protective mechanisms (Sumowski, 2015) that appear to engage later in the disease course.

A similar pattern emerged for self-reported disease impact. $\alpha 2$ spectral power mediated the CR-SVF relationship in PwMS reporting moderate physical and psychological disease impact, whereas under high psychological impact, CR's effect on SVF was independent of $\alpha 2$ power. Given evidence that CR moderates the depression-SVF relationship in MS (Biasi et al., 2025), this pattern may reflect mood-related alterations in oscillatory dynamics (Ippolito et al., 2022; Knyazev et al., 2006; Strijkstra et al., 2003) prompting CR to rely on alternate neuronal processes. Longitudinal studies are needed to clarify when and how CR's protective role intensifies, which factors, such as psychological ones, modulate it, and which individuals could benefit most from reserve-building or cognitive interventions.

The association between neuronal slowing and CR suggests that α oscillatory activity serves as a neurophysiological marker of cognitive resilience in PwMS, as individuals with higher CR exhibited $\alpha 2$ global power more comparable to that of HC. With growing interest in CR as a therapeutic target (Sumowski, 2015), identifying such electrophysiological markers is essential for evaluating the impact of reserve-enhancing interventions. The observed link between $\alpha 2$ power and leisure activity-derived CR further supports the potential of α oscillations as an objective measure of engagement in cognitively enriching activities.

Previous rsM/EEG studies have linked oscillatory activity to cognitive performance in PwMS (De Cock et al., 2023; Schoonhoven et al., 2019; Van Der Meer et al., 2013). We extend this work by showing that individuals with greater neuronal slowing perform worse on SVF. Earlier rsM/EEG studies including VF

found no associations, likely because they examined the phonemic component. While phonemic and semantic fluency share overlapping processes, they rely on partially distinct neural substrates. Phonemic fluency has been associated with inferior prefrontal regions (Biesbroek et al., 2016) and, in PwMS, with the caudate nucleus (Matías-Guiu et al., 2018); whereas semantic fluency involves the left anterior temporal lobe and the bilateral fusiform gyrus (Yee et al., 2018), areas showing widespread deviations in our data. Semantic fluency in PwMS is also linked to the thalamus (Matías-Guiu et al., 2018), a key generator of α activity (Hughes & Crunelli, 2005), which may explain why α activity correlated with semantic but not phonemic fluency in our study. Nonetheless, the electrophysiological interpretation of VF may require more complex functional models (Sjøgård et al., 2021), beyond spectral power estimation.

In essence, α_2 oscillatory activity emerges as both a marker and mechanism of CR in PwMS, reflecting neural preservation and cortical efficiency that sustain SVF. Reduced α_2 power indicates neuronal slowing, while preserved α_2 activity signifies cognitive resilience, offering a potential biomarker for monitoring and enhancing reserve through targeted interventions.

While our study advances understanding of the neurophysiological basis of CR, some limitations should be acknowledged. Structural brain measures, such as atrophy, were not included. Combining structural and functional data could clarify whether α oscillations directly reflect CR or broader neuroanatomical mechanisms (van Dam et al., 2021). The cross-sectional design limits causal inferences, warranting longitudinal studies to determine changes in CR's spectral signature over time. SVF was quantified using the total word count only, and further work should examine additional components, such as clustering and switching (Luo et al., 2010). Sex-related effects also warrant attention, given reported sex-related functional shifts in PwMS (Schoonheim et al., 2012) and the greater engagement of women with MS in cognitively enriching activities observed here. Finally, while we focused on α oscillations, other frequency bands, particularly θ , which shares a neurogenerative base with the α rhythm (Hughes & Crunelli, 2005) and correlates with memory in PwMS (Schoonhoven et al., 2019), may also contribute to CR and should be explored further.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, our findings demonstrate that neural preservation underlies CR and its protective effects on SVF in PwMS. Individuals with higher CR appear less susceptible to neuronal resource depletion, particularly at moderate levels of physical disability and disease impact. Identifying α oscillatory activity as a marker of cognitive resilience enables monitoring of reserve-building and informs personalized rehabilitation. Longitudinal studies should clarify whether enhancing CR through cognitive or behavioral interventions produces measurable neurophysiological changes. Collectively, our findings highlight the

need to extend cognitive assessments and interventions beyond processing speed to include lexico-semantic processes as an index of resilience.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alexandra Anagnostopoulou: Investigation, Data Curation, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Panagiotis E. Kartsidis:** Methodology, Formal Analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Nefeli Tsoukaki:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Maria Karagianni:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Nikos Melanitis:** Formal Analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Athanasia Liozidou:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Ioannis Nikolaidis:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Christos Chatzichristos:** Formal Analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Vahe Poghosyan:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Nikolaos Grigoriadis:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Panagiotis D. Bamidis:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Charis Styliadis:** Conceptualization, Funding Acquisition, Project Administration, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Acknowledgements

The authors extend their gratitude to the nursing staff of the Multiple Sclerosis Centre at AHEPA University General Hospital in Thessaloniki for their assistance with patient recruitment. We also thank all patients and healthy volunteers for their participation. This project was partly supported by the EU-funded RAISE Suite project (Grant Agreement no. 101188337).

Ethical Considerations

This study followed the framework of the MS-NEUROPLAST project, which was approved by the Research Ethics and Deontology Committee of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Protocol No. 254350/2020; approval 1 December 2020) and conducted in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration of Human Rights.

All copyrighted scales and questionnaires used in this study were employed with appropriate permission from the respective copyright holders. Material from the SDMT copyright © 1973, by Western Psychological Services. Reproduced by C Styliadis, PhD, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (CON1281), for specific, limited research use, under license of the publisher, WPS (rights@wpspublish.com). No additional reproduction, in whole or in part, by any medium or for any purpose, may be made without the prior, written authorization of WPS. All rights reserved. The MMSE, BVMT-R, and SNST were initially administered in this study using Greek translations not authorized by PAR. This has since been formally rectified through licensing, following proactive outreach by the research team to PAR. The MMSE, BVMT-R and SNST are copyrighted instruments and may not be

used or reproduced in whole or in part, in any form or language, or by any means without written permission of PAR.

Funding

This research project is supported by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (H.F.R.I.) under the “2nd Call for H.F.R.I. Research Projects to support Post-Doctoral Researchers” (Project Number: 314). This research was partially supported by the Horizon Europe Framework Program of the European Union under Grant Agreement no. 101058479.

Declaration of competing interests

All the authors except AA, IN, and CS declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as potential conflicts of interest. AA, PEK, IN, and CS disclose that they were supported by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (H.F.R.I.) under the “2nd Call for H.F.R.I. Research Projects to support Post-Doctoral Researchers” (Project Number: 314).

Data availability

The datasets of this study are not publicly available owing to the sensitive nature of the data and concerns of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), but are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

References

- Amato, M. P., Prestipino, E., Bellinvia, A., Nicolai, C., Razzolini, L., Pastò, L., Fratangelo, R., Tudisco, L., Fonderico, M., Mattiolo, P. L., Goretti, B., Zimatore, G. B., Losignore, N. A., Portaccio, E., & Lolli, F. (2019). Cognitive impairment in multiple sclerosis: An exploratory analysis of environmental and lifestyle risk factors. *PLoS ONE*, *14*(10).
<https://doi.org/10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0222929>
- Antony, M. M., Cox, B. J., Enns, M. W., Bieling, P. J., & Swinson, R. P. (1998). Psychometric properties of the 42-item and 21-item versions of the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales in clinical groups and a community sample. *Psychological Assessment*, *10*(2), 176–181. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1040-3590.10.2.176>

Asogbon, M. G., Huai, Y., Samuel, O. W., Jing, Z., Ma, Y., Liu, J., Jiang, Y., Fu, Y., Li, G., & Li, Y.

(2023). Analysis of Artifactual Components Rejection Threshold towards Enhanced Characterization of Neural Activity in Post-Stroke Survivor. *Proceedings of the Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society, EMBS*.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/EMBC40787.2023.10340688>

Babiloni, C., Del Percio, C., Capotosto, P., Noce, G., Infarinato, F., Muratori, C., Marcotulli, C.,

Bellagamba, G., Righi, E., Soricelli, A., Onorati, P., & Lupattelli, T. (2016). Cortical sources of resting state electroencephalographic rhythms differ in relapsing–remitting and secondary progressive multiple sclerosis. *Clinical Neurophysiology*, *127*(1), 581–590.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CLINPH.2015.05.029>

Babiloni, C., Ferri, R., Noce, G., Lizio, R., Lopez, S., Lorenzo, I., Panzavolta, A., Soricelli, A., Nobili, F.,

Arnaldi, D., Famà, F., Orzi, F., Buttinelli, C., Giubilei, F., Cipollini, V., Marizzoni, M., Guntekin, B., Akturk, T., Hanoğlu, L., ... Del Percio, C. (2021). Abnormalities of Cortical Sources of Resting State Alpha Electroencephalographic Rhythms are Related to Education Attainment in Cognitively Unimpaired Seniors and Patients with Alzheimer’s Disease and Amnesic Mild Cognitive

Impairment. *Cerebral Cortex*, *31*(4), 2220–2237. <https://doi.org/10.1093/CERCOR/BHAA356>

Babiloni, C., Lopez, S., Del Percio, C., Noce, G., Pascarelli, M. T., Lizio, R., Teipel, S. J., González-

Escamilla, G., Bakardjian, H., George, N., Cavedo, E., Lista, S., Chiesa, P. A., Vergallo, A.,

Lemercier, P., Spinelli, G., Grothe, M. J., Potier, M. C., Stocchi, F., ... Hampel, H. (2020). Resting-state posterior alpha rhythms are abnormal in subjective memory complaint seniors with preclinical Alzheimer’s neuropathology and high education level: the INSIGHT-preAD study. *Neurobiology of*

Aging, *90*, 43–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEUROBIOLAGING.2020.01.012>

- Benedict, R. H. B., Amato, M. P., DeLuca, J., & Geurts, J. J. G. (2020). Cognitive impairment in multiple sclerosis: clinical management, MRI, and therapeutic avenues. *The Lancet. Neurology*, *19*(10), 860. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(20\)30277-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(20)30277-5)
- Benjamini, Y., & Hochberg, Y. (1995). Controlling the False Discovery Rate: A Practical and Powerful Approach to Multiple Testing. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)*, *57*(1), 289–300. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2346101>
- Biasi, M. M., Taurisano, P., Manni, A., Mangialardi, V., Gasparre, D., Iaffaldano, P., Caputo, F., Iaffaldano, A., & Paolicelli, D. (2025). The protective role of cognitive reserve in moderating depressive symptomatology in patients with multiple sclerosis. *BMC Psychology*, *13*(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S40359-025-03162-5/TABLES/4>
- Biesbroek, J. M., van Zandvoort, M. J. E., Kappelle, L. J., Velthuis, B. K., Biessels, G. J., & Postma, A. (2016). Shared and distinct anatomical correlates of semantic and phonemic fluency revealed by lesion-symptom mapping in patients with ischemic stroke. *Brain Structure and Function*, *221*(4), 2123–2134. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S00429-015-1033-8/TABLES/5>
- Bizzo, B. C., Arruda-Sanchez, T., Topyne, S. M., Bireley, J. D., Lev, M. H., Gasparetto, E. L., & Klawiter, E. C. (2021). Anterior Insular Resting-State Functional Connectivity is Related to Cognitive Reserve in Multiple Sclerosis. *Journal of Neuroimaging*, *31*(1), 98–102. <https://doi.org/10.1111/JON.12779>
- Chiaravalloti, N. D., Genova, H. M., & DeLuca, J. (2015). Cognitive Rehabilitation in Multiple Sclerosis: The Role of Plasticity. *Frontiers in Neurology*, *6*(APR). <https://doi.org/10.3389/FNEUR.2015.00067>
- Cribari-Neto, F., & da Silva, W. B. (2011). A new heteroskedasticity-consistent covariance matrix estimator for the linear regression model. *AStA Advances in Statistical Analysis*, *95*(2), 129–146. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10182-010-0141-2/METRICS>

- De Cock, A., Van Ranst, A., Costers, L., Keytsman, E., D'Hooghe, M. B., D'Haeseleer, M., Nagels, G., & Van Schependom, J. (2023). Reduced alpha2 power is associated with slowed information processing speed in multiple sclerosis. *European Journal of Neurology*, *30*(9), 2793–2800.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ENE.15927>
- Delorme, A. (2023). EEG is better left alone. *Scientific Reports 2023 13:1*, *13*(1), 1–12.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-27528-0>
- Eijlers, A. J. C., Meijer, K. A., Van Geest, Q., Geurts, J. J. G., & Schoonheim, M. M. (2018). Determinants of Cognitive Impairment in Patients with Multiple Sclerosis with and without Atrophy. *https://Doi.Org/10.1148/Radiol.2018172808*, *288*(2), 544–551.
<https://doi.org/10.1148/RADIOL.2018172808>
- Fisk, J. D., Pontefract, A., Ritvo, P. G., Archibald, C. J., & Murray, T. J. (1994). The impact of fatigue on patients with multiple sclerosis. *The Canadian Journal of Neurological Sciences*, *21*(1), 9–14.
- Fuchs, T. A., Benedict, R. H. B., Bartnik, A., Choudhery, S., Li, X., Mallory, M., Oship, D., Yasin, F., Ashton, K., Jakimovski, D., Bergsland, N., Ramasamy, D. P., Weinstock-Guttman, B., Zivadinov, R., & Dwyer, M. G. (2019). Preserved network functional connectivity underlies cognitive reserve in multiple sclerosis. *Human Brain Mapping*, *40*(18), 5231. <https://doi.org/10.1002/HBM.24768>
- Gramfort, A., Luessi, M., Larson, E., Engemann, D. A., Strohmeier, D., Brodbeck, C., Goj, R., Jas, M., Brooks, T., Parkkonen, L., & Hämäläinen, M. (2013). MEG and EEG data analysis with MNE-Python. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, *7*(7 DEC), 70133.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/FNINS.2013.00267/BIBTEX>
- Greenberg, D. L., & Verfaellie, M. (2010). Interdependence of episodic and semantic memory: Evidence from neuropsychology. *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society : JINS*, *16*(5), 748.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S1355617710000676>

Hayes, A. F. (2013). *Introduction to Mediation, Moderation, and Conditional Process Analysis: A Regression-Based Approach* (T. D. Little, Ed.; Third). Guilford Press.

<https://www.guilford.com/books/Introduction-to-Mediation-Moderation-and-Conditional-Process-Analysis/Andrew-Hayes/9781462549030>

Hayes, A. F. ., & Little, T. D. . (2022). *Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis : a regression-based approach* (3rd ed.). The Guilford Press.

Hobart, J., Lamping, D., Fitzpatrick, R., Riazi, A., & Thompson, A. (2001). The Multiple Sclerosis Impact Scale (MSIS-29): a new patient-based outcome measure. *Brain : A Journal of Neurology*, *124*(Pt 5), 962–973. <https://doi.org/10.1093/BRAIN/124.5.962>

Hughes, S. W., & Crunelli, V. (2005). Thalamic Mechanisms of EEG Alpha Rhythms and Their Pathological Implications. <Http://Dx.DoI.Org/10.1177/1073858405277450>, *11*(4), 357–372. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1073858405277450>

Ippolito, G., Bertaccini, R., Tarasi, L., Di Gregorio, F., Trajkovic, J., Battaglia, S., & Romei, V. (2022). The Role of Alpha Oscillations among the Main Neuropsychiatric Disorders in the Adult and Developing Human Brain: Evidence from the Last 10 Years of Research. *Biomedicines*, *10*(12), 3189. <https://doi.org/10.3390/BIOMEDICINES10123189>

Jas, M., Engemann, D. A., Bekhti, Y., Raimondo, F., & Gramfort, A. (2017). Autoreject: Automated artifact rejection for MEG and EEG data. *NeuroImage*, *159*, 417–429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEUROIMAGE.2017.06.030>

Keune, P. M., Hansen, S., Weber, E., Zapf, F., Habich, J., Muenssinger, J., Wolf, S., Schönenberg, M., & Oschmann, P. (2017). Exploring resting-state EEG brain oscillatory activity in relation to cognitive functioning in multiple sclerosis. *Clinical Neurophysiology*, *128*(9), 1746–1754. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinph.2017.06.253>

- Knyazev, G. G., Savostyanov, A. N., & Levin, E. A. (2006). Alpha synchronization and anxiety: Implications for inhibition vs. alertness hypotheses. *International Journal of Psychophysiology*, 59(2), 151–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJPSYCHO.2005.03.025>
- Kosmidis, M. H., Vlahou, C. H., Panagiotaki, P., & Kiosseoglou, G. (2004). The verbal fluency task in the Greek population: Normative data, and clustering and switching strategies. *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society*, 10(2), 164–172. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1355617704102014>
- Kurtzke, J. F. (1983). Rating neurologic impairment in multiple sclerosis: An expanded disability status scale (EDSS). *Neurology*, 33(11), 1444–1452. <https://doi.org/10.1212/wnl.33.11.1444>
- Langdon, D. W., Amato, M. P., Boringa, J., Brochet, B., Foley, F., Fredrikson, S., Hämäläinen, P., Hartung, H. P., Krupp, L., Penner, I. K., Reder, A. T., & Benedict, R. H. B. (2012). Recommendations for a brief international cognitive assessment for multiple sclerosis (BICAMS). *Multiple Sclerosis Journal*, 18(6), 891–898. https://doi.org/10.1177/1352458511431076/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/10.1177_1352458511431076-FIG3.JPEG
- Leavitt, V. M., Simani, L., Koch, M., Morrow, S. A., Heuer, L., Roozbeh, M., Roozbeh, M., & Traynor, S. (2025). The language and memory test: A brief multidomain digital cognitive measure for multiple sclerosis. *Multiple Sclerosis (Houndmills, Basingstoke, England)*, 31(11), 1348–1357. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13524585251366096;CTYPE:STRING:JOURNAL>
- Lee, T.-W., Girolami, M., & Sejnowski, T. J. (1999). Independent Component Analysis using an Extended Infomax Algorithm for Mixed Sub - Gaussian and Super - Gaussian Sources. *Neural Computation*, 11(2), 409–433. <https://doi.org/10.1162/089976699300016719>
- Lezak, M. D., Howieson, D. B., Loring, D. W., Hannay, H. J., & Fischer, J. S. (2004). *Neuropsychological assessment* (4th ed.). Oxford University Press.

- Li, A., Feitelberg, J., Saini, A. P., Höchenberger, R., & Scheltienne, M. (2022). MNE-ICALabel: Automatically annotating ICA components with ICLabel in Python. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 7(76), 4484. <https://doi.org/10.21105/JOSS.04484>
- Lopez, S., Hampel, H., Chiesa, P. A., Del Percio, C., Noce, G., Lizio, R., Teipel, S. J., Dyrba, M., González-Escamilla, G., Bakardjian, H., Cavedo, E., Lista, S., Vergallo, A., Lemercier, P., Spinelli, G., Grothe, M. J., Potier, M. C., Stocchi, F., Ferri, R., ... Babiloni, C. (2024). The association between posterior resting-state EEG alpha rhythms and functional MRI connectivity in older adults with subjective memory complaint. *Neurobiology of Aging*, 137, 62–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEUROBIOLAGING.2024.02.008>
- Luo, L., Luk, G., & Bialystok, E. (2010). Effect of language proficiency and executive control on verbal fluency performance in bilinguals. *Cognition*, 114(1), 29–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COGNITION.2009.08.014>
- Maiovis, P., Ioannidis, P., Nucci, M., Gotzamani-Psarrakou, A., & Karacostas, D. (2016). Adaptation of the Cognitive Reserve Index Questionnaire (CRIq) for the Greek population. *Neurological Sciences*, 37(4), 633–636. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10072-015-2457-X/TABLES/3>
- Matías-Guiu, J. A., Cortés-Martínez, A., Montero, P., Pytel, V., Moreno-Ramos, T., Jorquera, M., Yus, M., Arrazola, J., & Matías-Guiu, J. (2018). Identification of Cortical and Subcortical Correlates of Cognitive Performance in Multiple Sclerosis Using Voxel-Based Morphometry. *Frontiers in Neurology*, 9, 408666. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FNEUR.2018.00920/BIBTEX>
- Nichols, T. E., & Holmes, A. (2002). Nonparametric permutation tests for functional neuroimaging: A primer with examples. *Human Brain Mapping*, 15(1), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.1058>
- Pascual-Marqui, R. D., Michel, C. M., & Lehmann, D. (1994). Low resolution electromagnetic tomography: a new method for localizing electrical activity in the brain. *International Journal of Psychophysiology*, 18(1), 49–65. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-8760\(84\)90014-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-8760(84)90014-X)

- Rocca, M. A., Riccitelli, G. C., Meani, A., Pagani, E., Del Sette, P., Martinelli, V., Comi, G., Falini, A., & Filippi, M. (2019). Cognitive reserve, cognition, and regional brain damage in MS: A 2 -year longitudinal study. *Multiple Sclerosis Journal*, *25*(3), 372–381.
https://doi.org/10.1177/1352458517750767/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/10.1177_1352458517750767-FIG1.JPEG
- Saldert, C., Giocondi, C., Van Ejsden, F., & Longoni, F. (2025). Experiences of Word-Finding Difficulties in Multiple Sclerosis: A Qualitative Interview Study. *International Journal of MS Care*, *210*.
<https://doi.org/10.7224/1537-2073.2024-069>
- Santangelo, G., Altieri, M., Enzinger, C., Gallo, A., & Trojano, L. (2019). Cognitive reserve and neuropsychological performance in multiple sclerosis: A meta-analysis. *Neuropsychology*, *33*(3), 379–390. <https://doi.org/10.1037/NEU0000520>
- Santangelo, G., Altieri, M., Gallo, A., & Trojano, L. (2019). Does cognitive reserve play any role in multiple sclerosis? A meta-analytic study. *Multiple Sclerosis and Related Disorders*, *30*, 265–276.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MSARD.2019.02.017>
- Schoonheim, M. M., Hulst, H. E., Landi, D., Ciccarelli, O., Roosendaal, S. D., Sanz-Arigita, E. J., Vrenken, H., Polman, C. H., Stam, C. J., Barkhof, F., & Geurts, J. J. G. (2012). Gender-related differences in functional connectivity in multiple sclerosis. *Multiple Sclerosis Journal*, *18*(2), 164–173.
https://doi.org/10.1177/1352458511422245/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/10.1177_1352458511422245-FIG4.JPEG
- Schoonheim, M. M., Meijer, K. A., & Geurts, J. J. G. (2015). Network Collapse and Cognitive Impairment in Multiple Sclerosis. *Frontiers in Neurology*, *6*(MAR).
<https://doi.org/10.3389/FNEUR.2015.00082>

Schoonhoven, D. N., Frascini, M., Tewarie, P., Uitdehaag, B. M. J., Eijlers, A. J. C., Geurts, J. J. G., Hillebrand, A., Schoonheim, M. M., Stam, C. J., & Strijbis, E. M. M. (2019). Resting-state MEG measurement of functional activation as a biomarker for cognitive decline in MS. *Multiple Sclerosis Journal*, *25*(14), 1896–1906.

https://doi.org/10.1177/1352458518810260/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/10.1177_1352458518810260-FIG4.JPEG

Sjøgård, M., Wens, V., Van Schependom, J., Costers, L., D’hooghe, M., D’haeseleer, M., Woolrich, M., Goldman, S., Nagels, G., & De Tiège, X. (2021). Brain dysconnectivity relates to disability and cognitive impairment in multiple sclerosis. *Human Brain Mapping*, *42*(3), 626–643.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/HBM.25247>

Stein, C., O’Keeffe, F., Strahan, O., McGuigan, C., & Bramham, J. (2023). Systematic review of cognitive reserve in multiple sclerosis: Accounting for physical disability, fatigue, depression, and anxiety. *Multiple Sclerosis and Related Disorders*, *79*, 105017.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MSARD.2023.105017>

Stern, Y., Arenaza-Urquijo, E. M., Bartrés-Faz, D., Belleville, S., Cantilon, M., Chetelat, G., Ewers, M., Franzmeier, N., Kempermann, G., Kremen, W. S., Okonkwo, O., Scarmeas, N., Soldan, A., Udeh-Momoh, C., Valenzuela, M., Vemuri, P., Vuoksimaa, E., Urquijo, E. M. A., Cantillon, M., ... Van Loenhoud, A. C. (2020). Whitepaper: Defining and investigating cognitive reserve, brain reserve, and brain maintenance. *Alzheimer’s & Dementia*, *16*(9), 1305–1311.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JALZ.2018.07.219>

Strijkstra, A. M., Beersma, D. G. M., Drayer, B., Halbesma, N., & Daan, S. (2003). Subjective sleepiness correlates negatively with global alpha (8–12 Hz) and positively with central frontal theta (4–8 Hz) frequencies in the human resting awake electroencephalogram. *Neuroscience Letters*, *340*(1), 17–20.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3940\(03\)00033-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3940(03)00033-8)

- Styliadis, C., Nikolaidis, I., Zilidou, V., Billis, A., Karagianni, M., Kartsidis, P. E., Anagnostopoulou, A., Liozidou, A., Poghosyan, V., Grigoriadis, N., & Bamidis, P. D. (2024). Advancing Precision in Cognitive Rehabilitation in Multiple Sclerosis: Protocol for a Two-arm, Parallel-Group, Single Blind Assessor, Randomised by Stratification Controlled Trial Investigating Computerised Cognitive Training Effects on Cortical Organisation, Cognition and Daily Function (MS-NEUROPLAST). *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-5369347/v1>
- Sumowski, J. F. (2015). Cognitive Reserve as a Useful Concept for Early Intervention Research in Multiple Sclerosis. *Frontiers in Neurology*, 6(Aug). <https://doi.org/10.3389/FNEUR.2015.00176>
- Sumowski, J. F., & Leavitt, V. M. (2013). Cognitive reserve in multiple sclerosis. *Multiple Sclerosis Journal*, 19(9), 1122–1127. https://doi.org/10.1177/1352458513498834/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/10.1177_1352458513498834-FIG3.JPEG
- Sumowski, J. F., Wylie, G. R., Deluca, J., & Chiaravalloti, N. (2009). Intellectual enrichment is linked to cerebral efficiency in multiple sclerosis: functional magnetic resonance imaging evidence for cognitive reserve. *Brain*, 133(2), 362. <https://doi.org/10.1093/BRAIN/AWP307>
- van Dam, M., Hulst, H. E., & Schoonheim, M. M. (2021). Coupling structure and function in early MS: How a less diverse repertoire of brain function could lead to clinical progression. *Multiple Sclerosis Journal*, 27(4), 491–493. https://doi.org/10.1177/1352458520987798/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/10.1177_1352458520987798-FIG1.JPEG
- Van Der Meer, M. L., Tewarie, P., Schoonheim, M. M., Douw, L., Barkhof, F., Polman, C. H., Stam, C. J., & Hillebrand, A. (2013). Cognition in MS correlates with resting-state oscillatory brain activity: An explorative MEG source-space study. *NeuroImage: Clinical*, 2(1), 727–734. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nicl.2013.05.003>

Yee, E., Jones, M. N., & McRae, K. (2018). Semantic Memory. *Stevens' Handbook of Experimental Psychology and Cognitive Neuroscience*, 1–38. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119170174.EPCN309>